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Wireless World Research Forum
Meeting 49

March 28th-30th 2023
Poznań, Poland

Towards sustainable and automated communications

Panel Discussion

**AI/Machine Learning-Enabled (CAV) in
the Era of 5G, 6G, and Beyond**
Organizer: Prof. S. Mohan

28 March 2023

About the speaker

- Bhavani Shankar M. R
 - PhD, Indian Institute of Science
 - Post Doc, KTH, Sweden
 - Assistant Professor, SnT
- Team Leader, SPARC group
 - Signal Processing Applications in Radar and Wireless Communications
 - 6 Post Docs, 5 PhDs
- Editor, Elsevier Signal Processing,
- Member EURASIP SAT on TMTSP, SAM-TC
- Founding member, ISAC ETI, IEEE Comsoc
- Domains of Interest: Signal Processing, Wireless Communications, Radar Signal Processing, Satellite systems

ADAS : Advance Driver Assisted Systems

Driver Monitoring

Vehicle-based intelligent safety systems that improve road safety at different phases

- Crash avoidance
- Crash severity mitigation and protection
- Post-crash

ADAS: THE CIRCLE OF SAFETY

- Long-Range Radar**
 - Adaptive Cruise Control
- Short/Medium-Range Radar**
 - Cross Traffic Alert
 - Rear Collision Warning
- LIDAR**
 - Emergency Braking
 - Pedestrian Detection
 - Collision Avoidance
- Cameras**
 - Traffic Sign Recognition
 - Lane Departure Warning
 - Park Assist
 - Surround View
- Ultrasound**
 - Park Assist

Exterior Sensing

https://ec.europa.eu/transport/road_safety/sites/roadsafety/files/pdf/ersosynthesis2018-adas.pdf
Swedish Transport Administration 2010

<https://www.electronicdesign.com/markets/automotive/article/21147200/nxp-semiconductors-the-role-of-machine-learning-in-autonomous-vehicles>. From Internet

When in ADAS effective

- Better information about environment

- Improved High-Res Sensing

- RADAR (long-range, short-range, M)
 - Camera (2D/ Time of Flight)
 - LIDAR, Ultrasonics

- Communication

- DSRC, CVX

- Better exploitation of information

- Processing

- Signal Processing
 - Machine Learning
 - Sensor Fusion

In-cabin Monitoring

- Level 4 Driver Assistance
 - Driver status monitoring, driver assistance, and takeover readiness
- Level 5 doesn't need a driver
 - Robust monitoring of all passengers

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Learning Techniques

- Complex and dense scenes
 - Driver attention
 - Multiple occupants
 - Variations in seating arrangement
- Use of Learning techniques
 - Follow rich image processing literature?
- Use of multiple sensors
 - Avoid Occlusions, better signal quality
 - Privacy preserving Radar
 - Radar data is not inherently images
 - Need good input for Learning algorithms
 - preprocessing and dynamic change of parameters
- Need sufficient data
 - Can it be simulated?
 - Digital Twin?

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